

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**THE STUDY OF CONSEQUENCES OF DIABETIC
KETOACIDOSIS IN CHILDREN**¹Aamna Qayyum, ²Sana Mushtaq, ³Ayesha Zujaja¹Nishtar Medical University, Multan., ²Nishtar Medical University, Multan., ³Nishtar Medical University, Multan.**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** December 2020 **Published:** January 2021**Abstract:**

Objective: This study aimed to establish the clinical profile, demographic data, and diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) in children under 18 years of age diagnosed with T1DM.

Place and Duration: This study was conducted in patients under 18 years of age diagnosed with T1DM with DKA in Nishtar Hospital Pediatrics Units, Multan from 1 May 2019 until 1 March 2020.

Materials and Methods: Clinical presentation, demographic characteristics, clinical presentations and laboratory findings were observed for all patients with DK1 T1DM. The patients admitted were under 18 years of age.

Results: A total of 60 T1DM children were examined with DKA. The mean case age was 8.9 years, with standard 1.7 years deviation. The number of patients aged 10 to 18 was 32 (53.3%), while 28 (46.6%) were under ten years. Of these, 20 (33.3%) were male, and 40 (66.6%) were female. 42 (70 percent) urban-owned patients and 18 (30%) rural patients. A total of 30 (50 per cent) newly diagnosed T1DM cases were identified. Polyuria 48 (80 per cent) and polydipsia 42 were the main symptoms recorded during hospitalization (70 per cent). At admission, the mean blood glucose was 407.35 mg/dl. Time for recovery was 22.3 hours. Hypokalemia 22 (36.6 per cent) and hypernatremia 18 were frequent complications (30 per cent).

Conclusions: If T1DM is used earlier to prevent DKA and its complications, it must be diagnosed.

Keywords: diabetic ketoacidosis, ketoacidosis, Type 1 diabetes mellitus

Corresponding author:**Aamna Qayyum,**

Nishtar Medical University, Multan.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Aamna Qayyum et al, *The Study Of Consequences Of Diabetic Ketoacidosis In Children*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2021; 08(1).

INTRODUCTION:

There has been an increase in type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) among children in recent times. Diabetes is at greater risk in middle-income countries such as Pakistan. Diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) is a severe diabetic complication, particularly T1DM (Bhardwaj, Yadav & Sharma 2017). The prevalence of DKA increases by 3 per cent each year amongst children. The DKA method for diagnosing the diagnosis is based on 2018's International Society of Pediatric and Adolescent Diabetes (ISPAD), the venous pH below 7.3, blood glucose above 11 mmol/L bicarbonate below 15 mmol/L (Bhardwaj, Yadav & Sharma 2017). There are three classes of DKA, i.e. mild, medium and severe. DKA Complications are not taken seriously even though the incidence of TD1M has increased (Naem 2017).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was conducted in patients under 18 years of age diagnosed with T1DM with DKA in Nishtar Hospital Pediatrics Units, Multan from 1 May 2019 until 1 March 2020. The case study did not cover parents/guardians who refused consent. Laboratory exams and clinical evaluations such as blood glucose, urine ketones, serum electrolytes, serum creatinine and serum electrolytes have been carried out. DKA was labelled as blood glucose > 200 mg/dL, pH less than 7.3, bicarbonate less than 15 mmol/L, and ketonuria. DKA resolution was classified as Mild DKA: blood pH between 7.21 and 7.30 or a bicarbonate level between 10 mmol/L and 15 mmol/L, depending on blood pH bicarbonate levels. Modern DKA: venous blood pH from 7.11 to 7.20 or from 5 mmol/L to 10 mmol/L of bicarbonate levels. Severe DKA: Venous blood pH <7,10 or 145mEq/l bicarbonate level, whereas serum potassium <3,5 mEq/l and >5mEq/l have been declared to be hypocalcemia and hyperkalemia, respectively. After an initial improvement, dilapidation in neurological function has been considered an alarming factor in diagnosing cerebral oedema. SPSS version 20.0 was used for analysis and data entry. Frequencies for qualitative variables have been calculated.

RESULTS:

A total of 60 T1DM children were examined with DKA. The mean case age was 8.9 years, with standard 1.7 years deviation. The number of patients aged 10 to 18 was 32 (53.3%), while 28 (46.6%) were under ten years. Of these, 20 (33.3%) were male, and 40 (66.6%) were female. 42 (70 percent) urban-owned patients and 18 (30%) rural patients. A total of 30 (50 per cent) newly diagnosed T1DM cases were identified. Polyuria 48 (80 per cent) and polydipsia 42 were the

main symptoms recorded during hospitalization (70 per cent). At admission, the mean blood glucose was 407.35 mg/dl. Time for recovery was 22.3 hours. Hypokalemia 22 (36.6 per cent) and hypernatremia 18 were frequent complications (30 per cent).

DISCUSSION:

DKA is considered to be the leading cause of death in T1DM.2 Case age was 8.9 years, and 53.3% between 10 to 18 years of age in the study. An analysis in Saudi Arabia is comparable to our report on the mean age of 11 years. Pulungan *et al.* (2018) and other authors found that the prevalence rate was higher among women, for example, with hormones such as the growth hormone and estrogen. Seventy per cent of patients were urban. Late diagnosis is responsible for the higher rate of mortality in cases of TD1M. Polyuria and polydipsia, vomiting and altered level of consciousness are the main symptoms of DKA. A study found respiratory distress in 23% of cases, while in other observations, it was 58.6% -87.1%. The most common type was severe DKA. Hypokalemia and Hyponatraemia were common complications. In various observations, the frequency of cerebral oedema fluctuated. We found cerebral oedema at 7.5%. Incidents that died during our study have been diagnosed recently with deranged serum creatinine. We found serum creatinine level in 6% of patients. We trust that our study will broaden our understanding of the DKA case profile in our area.

CONCLUSION:

The diagnosis of T1DM and its complications should not be underestimated to prevent the incidence of DKA.

REFERENCES:

1. Baker, P & Steck, A 2011, 'The past, present, and future of genetic associations in type 1 diabetes', *Curr diabetes reports*, vol 11, p. 445.
2. Bhardwaj, P, Yadav, V & Sharma, M 2017, 'Clinical profile and outcome of the children with diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) in hilly Himalayan state of north India', *Int J Res Med Sci*, vol 5, no. 12, pp. 5402-5.
3. Dunger, D, Sperling, M, Acerini, C, Bohn, D, Daneman, D & Danne, T 2004, 'European Society for PaediatricEndocrinology/Lawson Wilkins Pediatric Endocrine Society consensus statement on diabetic ketoacidosis in children and adolescents', *Pediatr*, vol 113, no. 1.
4. Jabbar, A, Farooqui, K, Habib, A, Islam, N, Haque, N & Akhter, J 2004, ' Clinical characteristics and outcomes of diabetic

- ketoacidosis in Pakistani adults with Type 2 diabetes mellitus', *Diabet Med*, vol 21, pp.920-3.
5. Lange, K, Swift, P, Pankowska, E & Danne, T 2014, 'Diabetes education in children and adolescents', *Pediatr Diabetes*, vol 25, pp. 77–85.
 6. Lone, S, Siddiqui, E, Muhammad, F, Atta, I, Ibrahim, M & Raza, J 2010, 'Frequency, clinical characteristics and outcome of diabetic ketoacidosis in children with type-1 diabetes at a tertiary care hospital', *J Pak Med Assoc*, vol 60, pp. 725-9.
 7. Naeem, M 2017, 'Update Regarding Diabetic Ketoacidosis in Children and Controversies in Management', *Qual Prim Care*, vol 26, no. 2, pp. 49-52.
 8. Naeem, M, Al-Alem, H, Al-Dubayee, M, AlJuraibah, F, Omair, A & Al-Ruwaili, A 2015, 'Characteristics of pediatric diabetic ketoacidosis in patients in Saudi Arabia', *Saudi Med J*, vol 36, no. 1, pp. 20-5.
 9. Naveed, D, Bilal, N, Nasir, B & Lodhi, B 2009, 'Precipitating factors for diabetic ketoacidosis', *KUST Med J*, vol 1, pp. 6-8.
 10. Newhook, L, Curtis, J, Hagerty, D, Grant, M, Paterson, A & Crummel, C 2004, 'High incidence of childhood type 1 diabetes in the Avalon Peninsula, Newfoundland, Canada', *Diabetes Care*, vol 27, pp. 885-8.
 11. Niaz, Z, Razzaq, A, Chaudhary, U, Awais, M, Yaseen, M & Naseer, I 2005, 'Mortality review of diabetic ketoacidosis in Mayo Hospital, Lahore - Pakistan', *Biomedica*, vol 21, pp. 83-5.
 12. Ogurtsova, K, da Rocha, F, Huang, Y, Linnenkamp, U, Guariguata, L & Cho, N 2017, 'IDF Diabetes Atlas:Global estimates for the prevalence of diabetes for 2015 and 2040', *Diabetes Res ClinPract*, vol 128, pp. 40–50.
 13. Onyiriuka, A & Ifebi, E 2013, 'Ketocidosis at diagnosis of type 1 diabetes in children and adolescents: frequency and clinical characteristics', *J Diabetes MetabDisord*, vol 12, no. 1, p. 47.
 14. Otieno, C, Kayima, J, Omonge, E & Oyoo, G 2005, 'Diabetic ketoacidosis: risk factors, mechanisms and management strategies in sub-Saharan Africa: a review', *East Afr Med J*, vol 82, no. 12 Suppl, pp.S197– 203.
 15. Pulungan, A, Batubara, J, Tridjaja, B, Soesanti, F, Fadiana, G & Annisa, D 2019, 'Profile of Diabetic Ketoacidosis in Children with Diabetes Mellitus in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Jakarta: A Retrospective Study', *Acta Scientific Paediatr*, vol 2, no. 2, pp. 24-9.
 16. Pulungan, A, Juwita, E, Pudjiadi, A, Rahmayanti, S & Tsaniya, I 2018, 'Diabetic Ketoacidosis in Adolescents and Children: A Prospective Study of Blood versus Urine Ketones in Monitoring Therapeutic Response', *Acta Med Indones*, vol 50, no. 1, pp. 46-52.
 17. Qayyum, A, Lone, S, Ibrahim, M, Atta, I & Raza, J 2010, 'Effects of diabetes self management education on glycaemic control in children with insulindependent diabetes mellitus', *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak*, vol 20, pp. 802-5.
 18. Razavi, Z 2010, 'Frequency of ketoacidosis in newly diagnosis type 1 diabetic children', *Oman Med J*, vol 25, no. 2, pp. 114–7.
 19. Razavi, Z & Hamidi, F 2017, 'Diabetic Ketoacidosis: Demographic Data, Clinical Profile and Outcome in a Tertiary Care Hospital', *Iran J Pediatr*, vol 27, no. 3, p. e7649.
 20. Schober, E, Rami, B & Waldhoer, T 2010, 'Austrian Diabetes Incidence Study G. Diabetic ketoacidosis at diagnosis in Austrian children in 1989-2008: a population-based analysis', *Diabetologia*, vol 53, no. 6, pp. 1057–61.
 21. Sheikh, A & Malloush, A 2009, 'Diabetic ketoacidosis: more cases seen during summer vacation', *Pak J Med Sci*, vol 25, pp. 512-5.
 22. Shera, A, Miyan, Z, Basit, A, Maqsood, A, Ahmadani, M & Fawwad, A 2008, 'Trends of type 1 diabetes in Karachi, Pakistan.', *Pediatr Diabetes*, vol 9, pp. 401-6.
 23. Varadajan, P & Suresh, S 2015, 'Delayed diagnosis of diabetic ketoacidosis in children – a cause for concern', *Int J Diabetes Dev C*, vol 32, no. 2, pp. 66-70.
 24. Wolfsdorf, J, Glaser, N, Agus, M, Fritsch, M, Hanas, R & Rewers, A 2018, 'ISPAD Clinical Practice Consensus Guidelines 2018: Diabetic ketoacidosis and the hyperglycemic hyperosmolar state', *Pediatr Diabetes*, vol 19, no. Suppl.27, pp. 155–77.